

Primer: Conducting an Individual Participant Data Meta-Analysis

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What is an individual participant data meta-analysis?

The goal of any meta-analysis is to summarize the evidence in multiple studies that address the same research question. In a conventional meta-analysis, results are combined using aggregate data (AD) from the individual studies, typically summary statistics of the study results (e.g., means, effect sizes, confidence intervals). By contrast, an Individual Patient Data Meta-Analysis (IPDMA) gathers individual participant data (IPD) from each study and analyses them jointly, allowing for additional and more precise analyses.

Why is it relevant?

An IPDMA is considered the ‘gold standard’ for systematic reviews and meta-analysis (Higgins et al., 2024). An IPDMA uses the most detailed level of data available, which can lead to more reliable and less biased results than AD analyses. By centrally collecting, validating, and re-analyzing individual data from multiple trials, an IPDMA provides for a larger number of observations, allows for systematic co-variate analyses not possible with AD alone, and may help counter shortcomings in the reporting of the original studies. IPDMA are most established for clinical trials, but they can provide high-quality evidence in any area where data from individual participants in multiple studies can be combined. With the advent of open research data and professionally managed research data repositories, IPDMA projects are becoming more feasible. Also, novel federated learning methods and infrastructures facilitate maintaining high data protection standards in IPDMA studies. Still, conducting an IPDMA remains a complex and resource-intensive process that requires careful planning from the outset. This primer collects relevant resources and outlines the steps for planning and conducting an IPDMA.

How to conduct an IPDMA?

Table 1: Summary of key steps in conducting an IPDMA

1. Planning and Preparation

- Define objectives, eligibility criteria (e.g., PICO framework)
- Develop a protocol, obtain ethical approval (e.g., PRISMA guidelines)
- Identify and screen eligible trials (e.g., COCHRANE guidelines)
- Decide data needs, set up data dictionaries (e.g., SPHN Semantic Interoperability Framework)

2. Collaboration and retrieval of individual participant data

- Establish a collaboration
- Follow responsible data sharing principles, request IPD (e.g., sharing platforms like Vivli)
- Set up data sharing and transfer agreements (e.g., SPHN templates)

3. Managing individual participant data

- Check data (validity and consistency) and assess risk of bias
- Harmonize data (syntax, structure and terminology)

4. Statistical implementation

- Implement the planned statistical approach within the chosen framework (e.g., one- or two-stage approaches, federated data)

5. Reporting

- Adhere to PRISMA-IPD reporting guidelines
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1. Planning and preparation

1.1 Define objectives and eligibility criteria

An IPDMA needs a clearly defined research question to determine the eligibility of individual studies to be included. One recommended approach is to use a framework like PICO. PICO is used in Cochrane Reviews to structure health research questions based on four components: Patient/Population, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome. It helps define inclusion criteria, guide search strategies, and categorize studies. Cochrane Reviews use three types of PICO models: Review PICOs, Comparison PICOs, and Included Study PICOs (see <https://www.cochranelibrary.com/about-pico>).

1.2 Develop a protocol and obtain ethics approval

Develop a protocol that describes all planned steps in conducting and reporting the IPDMA. Whenever possible, follow up-to-date standards for your specific discipline. For example, for clinical trials, the SPIRIT (Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials) guidelines list items related to administrative information, introduction, methods, and ethics. Note that in the updated version of April 2025, a new section titled ‘open science’ has been added with a number of items related to data sharing and dissemination.

The protocol should list how the individual participant data will be managed and what statistical analyses will be conducted. Alternatively, these items can be specified in a separate Data Management Plan and Statistical Analysis Plan (see section 3 and subsection 4.3). The protocol also needs to specify how ethical approval will be obtained, if and how consent of participants will be obtained, and how amendments to and deviations from the protocol will be communicated.

1.3 Screen and identify eligible trials

Ideally, an IPDMA should be based on IPD from *all* relevant studies and only relevant studies. Typically this requires conducting a *Systematic Review* (see the CRS Primer on Systematic Reviews Ineichen et al. (2023)).

For clinical trials, Cochrane provides guidelines on how to perform a sensitive search and obtain published and unpublished data <https://training.cochrane.org/handbook/current/chapter-04>. Trial registries or regulatory bodies can also be an initial place to start the search, e.g., the International Clinical Trials Registry platform <https://clinicaltrials.gov/>, the US Food and Drug administration (FDA), or the European Medicines Agency (EMA).

1.4 Decide what data you need and set up a data dictionary

Before obtaining the data it is important to think what variables in the IPD will be required and how they will be defined without ambiguity and in a structured manner. A data dictionary will be essential metadata and should be planned in advance. The dictionary should describe the meaning of each variable, its format and possible values. In its simplest form, a data dictionary can be a table with columns indicating *variable* (e.g., Age at randomization), *variable name* (e.g., Age) and *definition* (e.g., Numeric, in years, NA = unknown). The dictionary should adopt existing conventions when possible. Examples of international standard vocabularies for clinical health information are SNOMED CT and LOINC. A further step towards interoperability is the use of simple grammar and rules to describe the relation between the concepts in the dictionary. For comprehensive guidelines and concept data sets, refer to the Semantic Interoperability Framework created by the Data Coordination Center (DCC) of the Swiss Personalized Health Network (SPHN).

2. Collaboration and retrieval of individual participant data

The collaboration with investigators of the individual original studies to obtain IPD takes substantial time and effort. Thinking about these steps in advance can help making the collaboration more efficient.

2.1 Establish a collaboration

Consider original investigators as active participants in a formal collaboration rather than passive providers of data (Maxwell et al., 2024), and clarify eventual authorship in planned publications early. Good communication of the project features, planning and scope are very important at the initial contact stage. Early contacts can also help clarifying any aspects of the original study design to ensure that it is eligible. Subsequent formal invitations to collaborate usually involve sharing a draft of the protocol, statistical analysis plan, data management plan and data dictionary, and the project timeline. Try to obtain feedback from the original investigators that can be taken into account. Also, data transfer and sharing agreements can be discussed at this point.

2.2 Responsible data sharing principles

In 2013, the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA) and the Pharmaceutical Research and Manufacturers of America (PhRM) released a statement describing a series of **responsible data sharing principles** (see statement). While conceived for pharmaceutical research, we recommend adhering to these principles in any IPDMA:

- Safeguarding the privacy of patients (participants)
- Respecting the integrity of national regulatory systems
- Maintaining incentives for investment in original research

These principles apply to both those requesting IPD and those contributing to it.

2.3 IPD requests

There are two main ways IPD can be requested:

Requests via personal contact. Ventresca et al. (2020) provide practical guidance for contacting authors of original studies. Among other things, the purpose of the project should be clearly communicated and when possible, the study protocol and similar key documents can be included already in the request email.

Requests via data repository or data-sharing platforms. Many research institutions are collaborating with data sharing platforms (or developing their own) to improve efficiency and transparency in handling data sharing requests. These platforms facilitate sharing of high-quality data while preserving patient privacy and confidentiality. Examples of such platforms for clinical trial data are:

- The Clinical Study Data Request (CSDR) consortium offers data from several pharmaceutical companies and clinical study funders.
- The Yale University Open Data Access (YODA) project has iteratively developed a model for responsible data sharing.
- Vivli, a global clinical research data sharing platform focused on sharing IPD from completed clinical trials. The platform acts as neutral intermediary between data contributors, data users and the broader community. It evolved from a project from The Multi-Regional Clinical Trials Center of Brigham and Women's Hospital and Harvard (MRCT Center).

2.4 Data sharing and data transfer agreements

Data sharing and transfer agreements can become extensive and complicated, and sometimes rich in legal terminology. We provide a simple checklist of the most important items. Some consortia, organizations and IPDMA researchers are publishing **templates**:

- The SPHN provides several legal agreement templates for multicenter projects. See <https://sphn.ch/services/dtua>.
- The authors of the book *Individual participant data (IPD) meta-analysis* (Riley et al., 2021) provide multiple templates for different aspects of IPDMA project management, including email IPD and collaboration requests, and transfer agreements. See <https://www.ipdma.co.uk/templates>.
- An illustrative toolkit for IPDMA provides templates for letters of agreement (Maxwell et al., 2024).
- Cochrane provides templates for data collection forms for reviews of randomized clinical trials. See <https://training.cochrane.org/data-collection-form-rcts>.

Data sharing agreement checklist

- responsibilities and obligations
- data to be exchanged
- data access
- platform / protocol for transfer
- timelines and deadlines
- provisions for third-party sharing
- intellectual property rights
- data format
- filenaming convention
- instructions to de-identify data
- no* label/code for reidentification

3. Managing individual participant data

Managing the often heterogeneous IPD requires substantial time and expertise. We highly recommend involving a research data expert or data steward in the process. A data management strategy should be already outlined in the planning phase of an IPDMA and be part of the protocol or a data management plan. The SPIRIT protocol guidelines (Chan et al., 2025) include a Data Management item in their checklist, which refers to plans for data entry, coding, security, and storage, including any related processes to promote data quality.

3.1 Checking data

Several data checks need to be conducted upon retrieval of IPDs and in later stages of an IPDMA.

- A good *initial check* is to clarify whether missing variables were not collected in the original study or whether they were not provided for the IPDMA.
- Check the *validity, range and consistency of variables*. This includes looking for implausible, invalid, or outlying values. It should be verified that the variable recoding for the IPDMA did not introduce any data errors. Compare descriptive summary statistics with the original study to verify the number of participants and the distribution of variables.
- In randomized controlled trials, conducting a *risk of bias assessment* is strongly recommended to evaluate the internal validity of the studies, that is, whether their results may be biased (Levis et al., 2024).

3.2 Data pooling and data harmonization

Data pooling refers to bringing together data from multiple sources into a single dataset. This often requires making data sets from heterogeneous sources comparable, also known as *data harmonization* (Adhikari et al., 2021; Cheng et al., 2024). In short, we can understand data harmonization as resolving heterogeneity along three **dimensions**:

- *Syntax* or data format, for example, CSV, JSON or HTML. Some of these technical formats may need additional preprocessing before data can be harmonized.

- *Structure* or conceptual schema of the data. This refers, for example, whether data are highly organized (e.g., tables) or have no fixed format (e.g., text). In tabular data, this includes how to represent variables and events across rows and columns.
- *Semantics and terminology*. This refers to the use of the same terms to define the same concepts (e.g., the category *young adult* may refer to people under 30 in one data set and people between 18 and 25 in another data set). In tabular data, a data dictionary explaining the meaning of each variable is necessary for data harmonization.

There are some important **tradeoffs** that should be considered when harmonizing the data. Harmonization can result in larger data volumes, improved statistical power, generalizability, and accessibility. It can also identify and rectify miscodings or biases in original data collection processes, improving data quality. However, data harmonization has the risk of oversimplifying complex concepts and introducing measurement errors or a loss in precision or validity. Limitations arise when harmonized data inherits the shortcomings of the original datasets or introduce biases. For example, harmonized datasets often include only a subset of data from what could theoretically be collected (e.g., a geographical bias of data availability). To navigate these challenges in data harmonization, cooperative partnerships and awareness of context-specific limitations are crucial.

4. Statistical analysis

There are two statistical approaches to perform an IPDMA. The approach and the specific model should be specified a priori at the protocol stage (Higgins et al., 2024). Both approaches have their own set of advantages and disadvantages that are thoroughly discussed in the literature (see a recent discussion in Riley et al. (2023)). The key elements are summarized in Table 2. A catalog of **software** packages and example code for different aspects of the statistical analysis in an IPDMA can be found in the webpage <https://www.ipdma.co.uk/software-code> provided by Riley et al. (2021).

IPDMA	One-stage approach	Two-stage approach
Description	Analyze all participant data simultaneously in a single model.	Analyze each study separately, then aggregate study-level estimates.
Advantages	More precise estimates; better for exploring interactions.	Simpler; clear within- and between-study separation.
Limitations	Computationally intensive; complex modeling required.	Less efficient with rare outcomes or few studies.
Data handling	Requires pooling and harmonization of all datasets.	Pool study-specific estimates in meta-analysis.
Typical models	Hierarchical/mixed-effects models (e.g., GLMM).	Standard meta-analysis models on study-level estimates.

Table 2: Comparison of One-stage and Two-stage IPD Meta-Analyses

4.1 Two-stage IPDMA

In a two-stage IPDMA the IPD from each study is first analyzed separately to obtain summary data with study-specific estimates (e.g., effect estimates and their confidence intervals). Subgroup effects within each study can be analyzed at this stage. In the second stage, these estimates are combined using standard meta-analytic models like random or fixed-effect models. Unlike the standard meta-analysis based on AD, this approach allows investigating interactions between treatment effects and certain characteristics of the participants. The advantage of this approach compared to the one-stage IPDMA is that it is relatively simple to implement and there is a clear separation between within-study and between-study analysis, however, the one-stage approach has been recommended when most studies in the IPDMA have few participants or events (Riley et al., 2023).

4.2 One-stage IPDMA

In a one-stage IPDMA all participant-level data from the included studies are analyzed simultaneously within a single statistical model. The models used are typically hierarchical or multilevel, for example, a hierarchical random effects model that accounts for clustering of participants within studies. This approach has more power than the two-stage approach when investigating complex interactions, e.g., treatment-covariate interactions. It is also more flexible regarding the model assumptions and specification. A limitation is that this approach is computationally intensive and may require complex modeling techniques, especially when dealing with large datasets or many covariates. A one-stage IPDMA requires harmonization of the data from the individual studies.

4.3 Missing data

Missing covariate data are frequently encountered in IPDMA: some variables may not have been collected in some studies due to different designs and target variables. Another type of missing data is sporadically missing data within individual studies. The choice of how to handle missing data and the specific approach or method used can influence the results of an IPDMA and should be carefully considered already in the protocol or statistical analysis plan. We refer to the relevant methodological literature, e.g., Burgess et al. (2013); Quartagno and Carpenter (2016); Debray et al. (2021).

4.4 Federated approaches

Data sensitivity and privacy are key factors affecting the implementation of an IPDMA, especially in health and clinical research. Federated Learning (FL) is a machine-learning framework where the analysis or model fitting is performed decentralized and only the resulting model parameters are shared. FL has been proposed for multi-institutional collaborations in health care because it can enhance data privacy and security (Pati et al., 2024). Based on the principle of FL, a federated meta-analysis methodological framework enables the analysis of IPD without requiring physical data sharing (Pietrobon et al., 2025).

The implementation of such a federated approach is not yet widespread and studies on real-world clinical applications are limited (Teo et al., 2024). Also, FL is not exempt from privacy risks, and appropriate mitigation techniques must be evaluated on a case-by-case basis, with each solution requiring careful configuration and a thorough assessment of cost-benefit trade-offs (Pati et al., 2024). Despite these limitations, federated data approaches offer promising solutions to support legal and privacy compliance in IPDMA projects.

5. Reporting

As in any systematic review or meta-analysis, comprehensive reporting of methods and results is critical. We recommend adhering to the PRISMA-IPD guidelines (Stewart et al., 2015), which are an extension of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) statement, specific to IPD.

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